

OpenStreetMap data for automated labelling of machine learning examples: The challenge of road type imbalance

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Advances in Artificial Intelligence (AI) and, specifically, in Deep Learning (DL) have fostered geospatial analysis and remote sensing, culminating in the establishment of GeoAI [1,2] and the solidification of research on methodologies and techniques for AI-assisted mapping [3-7]. Nevertheless, a particular challenge lies in the substantial demand for training examples in DL. Manual labelling of these examples is labour-intensive, consuming a considerable amount of time and financial resources. Alternatively, semi or automated labelling of data emerges as a prominent solution, as exemplified by the tool *ohsome2label* [8], which harnesses data from the OpenStreetMap [9] to label satellite images. However, moving from characterising object types (road, river, building) based on geometry to categorising them by attributes might result in an imbalanced class distribution in the utilised Machine Learning (ML) dataset.

Such imbalances are common in numerous practical applications. Learning from skewed datasets can be particularly challenging and often requires non-conventional ML techniques. A comprehensive awareness of the issues associated with class imbalance, as well as strategies for mitigating them, is essential [10]. In the context of spatial data, the distribution of classes can vary from country to country and region to region, adding a new layer of complexity and exacerbating this issue.

In this context, an analysis was conducted on the distribution of road types, defined by the values of the OSM "highway" tag, in diverse-profile nations. The aim was to evaluate the extent of class imbalance and to identify any consistent patterns in the distribution of road types used by mappers.

The initial hypothesis posits the existence of distinctive distribution patterns of road types, which are linked to the unique socioeconomic and cultural aspects of each country.

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Another consideration is the voluntary nature of OSM data production, frequently carried out by individuals who map remote areas using solely remotely sensed images.

In this study, nine countries with diverse profiles were selected through random stratification, taking into account their unique characteristics across different continents. The goal was to capture a wide range of socioeconomic and cultural scenarios. From the Northern Hemisphere, Germany, Great Britain, Italy, and the United States were chosen, while Brazil, Chile, Ethiopia, India, and Sudan represented the Southern Hemisphere.

To conduct the study, the *ohsome* platform [11] was employed, facilitating the retrieval of historical statistics from OSM data, in collaboration with the *ohsome-Dashboard* interface [12], which enables rapid generation of metrics related to the discussed issue.

The experiment was set up in the *ohsome-Dashboard* with the following parameters, quantifying the overall road length grouped by tag: `OSM_tag: "highway=*"; OSM_type: "object=way"; measure: "length"; results grouping: "by tag"; time interval: "2023-01-01T00:00:00Z - 2023-07-16T20:00:00Z"; Period: "quarterly"`.

From the results, a significant variation in the number of distinct tags adopted by each country is observed initially, namely: Brazil 49; Chile 38; Ethiopia 31; Germany 73; Great Britain 55; India 48; Italy 64; Sudan 22; and United States 73. Due to that, the analysis was restricted to the top 10 tags with the highest percentage extension in each country, identifying four unique tag values as most frequent: *unclassified*, *track*, *residential*, and *service* (see Figure 1).

The tag *unclassified* emerges as the most frequent of all, particularly prevalent in Brazil, Ethiopia, and Sudan (45.5%, 35.5%, and 37.7%, respectively). That tag value ranks second in countries such as Chile (16.9%), India (24.4%), and Italy (16.4%), while also featuring among the top five tags in three other nations: Germany (5th - 5.5%), Great Britain (5th - 12.0%), and United States (4th - 7.3%). The tag *track* emerges as the dominant one in terms of extension in Germany (45.2%), Chile (31.0%), and Italy (28.7%), also positioning itself among the top five most used tags in other nations. The third most frequent tag is *residential*, with percentages of 34.2% in the United States and 24.4% in India, also placing among the top five tags in other territories. Lastly, the tag *service* manifests as the most frequent in Great Britain, constituting 18.1% of the total road extension in the country. A broad analysis of the results reveals class imbalance in eight out of the nine selected countries. An exception to this scenario is observed in Great Britain, where a balanced distribution is found across the top five highway classes ranging from 18.1% to 12.0%.

The tag *unclassified* stands out from the others by being among the top two most frequent tags in six out of the nine nations considered. On the whole, this tag exhibits lower proportions in Northern Hemisphere countries and higher proportions in Southern Hemisphere countries. However, Chile and Italy deviate from this generalisation, revealing similar percentage proportions.

With the aim of establishing a link between tag frequency and the socioeconomic and cultural aspects of a nation, which could serve as a coarse proxy in an ML model, a comparison was drawn between the proportions of the aforementioned tag and the Human Development Index (HDI). This resulted in a negative correlation with an R^2 value of 0.62. In the graph that illustrates the relationship between HDI and the proportion of the *unclassified* tag, Brazil emerges as an outlier. When Brazilian data is excluded from the analysis, the R^2 value rises to 0.93, indicating a strong correlation for the remaining countries.

Figure 1. Top Ten Highway Tag Distributions by Country and Relationship of *Unclassified* Tag to HDI.

One hypothesis explaining Brazil's non-conformity lies in the country's internal heterogeneity, marked by distinct territorial occupation patterns, such as small and medium-sized agricultural properties in the South and Southeast, as well as vast properties in the Midwest. Another possibility would be an incorrect interpretation of the term unclassified instead of the term "road" (roads with unknown classification). However, a more detailed investigation of this issue is beyond the scope of this work.

To explain the relationship between HDI and the frequency of the tag unclassified two approaches could be employed. Firstly, assuming that the data on OSM reflects the reality, low values of HDI would be related to sparse urbanisation, and therefore a relatively elevated number of small settlements far apart from each other, leading to an increased proportion of roads of unclassified type. Another possibility would be, like for Brazil, a miss-concept use of the term unclassified, that would be related to a lower education level, reflected by a low value of HDI.

In the context of automatic labelling of examples for ML, the results underscore the necessity for careful evaluation of class (tag) distribution, as well as the caution required when utilising pre-trained ML models in diverse geographical regions.

Furthermore, these findings can be extrapolated to other OSM objects, like buildings and Land Use Land Cover (LULC), where class imbalance might arise due to the socio-economic and cultural traits of the region or country.

The investigation of the theme addressed in this study assumes an even greater level of significance when contemplating the growing application of AI-assisted mapping techniques. Specifically, when AI models are trained using OSM data for labelling ML examples, and subsequently the resultant mapped data is integrated back into the OSM database, it has the potential to lead to a vicious cycle.

To address those concerns, several avenues for future research have been identified: broadening the assessment of class imbalance across different nations and object categories, to identify anomalous patterns; developing methods and tools to semantically and topologically evaluate the data coherence and consistency in OSM.

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